

Comparison of Airway Nebulization with Ropivacaine or Lignocaine on Intubation Responses in Patients Undergoing Surgery under General Anaesthesia

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Abstract:

Background: Endotracheal intubation and extubation are associated with significant hemodynamic responses and airway irritation, potentially leading to complications such as hypertension, tachycardia, and coughing. Effective management of these responses is crucial for patient safety and comfort during surgery. This study aims to compare the effects of airway nebulization with ropivacaine versus lignocaine on intubation and extubation responses in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia.

Methods: A total of 64 patients scheduled for elective surgery under general anesthesia were randomly assigned to two groups: Group A received 5 ml of 0.75% ropivacaine nebulization, while Group B received 5 ml of 2% lignocaine nebulization. Hemodynamic parameters (heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, oxygen saturation) and laryngeal irritation (coughing) were monitored during intubation and extubation. Data were analyzed using SPSS 24, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: Group A (ropivacaine) demonstrated significantly better control of hemodynamic parameters compared to Group B (lignocaine). Heart rate and blood pressure were significantly lower in Group A at multiple time points post-intubation and post-extubation (p < 0.05). Laryngeal irritation was also reduced in Group A, with fewer incidences of coughing.

Conclusion: Ropivacaine nebulization is more effective than lignocaine in managing hemodynamic responses and reducing laryngeal irritation during intubation and extubation in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia. These findings support the use of ropivacaine for better perioperative airway management.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and diverse patient populations are recommended to validate these findings and explore the long-term benefits of ropivacaine nebulization in various surgical settings.

Keywords: Ropivacaine, Lignocaine, Intubation, Extubation, Hemodynamic responses, Airway nebulization, General anesthesia.

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Introduction

Endotracheal intubation and extubation are critical procedures in the administration of general anesthesia, first clinically utilized by William Macewen in 1880 [1]. Over time, the introduction of muscle relaxants has greatly facilitated these procedures, making them common place in operating theatres and intensive care units worldwide. However, intubation and extubation are associated with various circulatory and airway responses due to reflex sympathetic activity, which can lead to complications such as coughing, agitation, bronchospasm, tachycardia, hypertension, arrhythmias, myocardial ischemia, and increased intracranial and intraocular pressures.

The hemodynamic responses, particularly the sudden increase in heart rate and blood pressure, are primarily due to the surge of catecholamines and airway irritation during laryngoscopy, tracheal intubation, and extubation. The incidence of coughing during emergence from anesthesia is reported to range from 67% to 80%, posing significant discomfort and physiological stress on patients [2]. Consequently, various pharmacological interventions have been explored to mitigate these adverse effects, including intravenous lignocaine, short-acting opioids like fentanyl and remifentanyl, beta-blockers such as esmolol and labetalol, and local anesthetics.

Nebulization, a non-invasive method, has gained attention for its potential in reducing adverse airway responses due to its ability to deliver medication directly to the respiratory tract, producing low serum levels and fewer systemic side effects. Among local anesthetics, lignocaine has been widely used due to its intermediate duration of action. However, its effects may not last through the extubation period if administered pre-induction [3]. Ropivacaine, a long-acting amide local anesthetic, offers a promising alternative with a potentially longer duration of action, making it more effective in blunting airway reflexes and inhibiting hemodynamic responses during extubation.

Recent studies have highlighted the efficacy of ropivacaine in various surgical settings. For instance, a study demonstrated that topical ropivacaine significantly reduced hemodynamic responses and the incidence of coughing during extubation compared to normal saline [4]. Similarly, a study reported that nebulized ropivacaine was more effective than lignocaine in controlling hemodynamic responses during intubation and extubation in patients undergoing elective surgeries [5].

This research aims to compare the effects of airway nebulization with ropivacaine versus lignocaine on intubation and extubation responses in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a quantitative, randomized, prospective, comparative, interventional study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of 6 months in the operation theatres of Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS).

Participants: Participants included patients scheduled for elective surgery under general anesthesia.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients undergoing elective surgery under general anesthesia.
- Age between 18 and 65 years.
- ASA physical status I and II.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patient refusal.
- History of hypersensitivity to study drugs.
- Patients with congestive heart failure, heart block, arrhythmia, congenital heart disease, cardiac pacemaker, asthma, and COPD.
- Obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²).

- Patients with anticipated difficult intubation.
- Surgery lasting more than 3 hours.
- Emergency procedures.

Bias: To minimize bias, the study utilized computer-based randomization and double blinding.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{2(Z\alpha + Z\beta)^2 S^2}{d^2}$$

Z α =1.96 at 95% confidence level

Z β = 0.84 at 80% power

S=Standard deviation of HR on extubation¹⁶

d= mean difference of HR on extubation¹⁶

Procedure

1. Preoperative Phase:

- Pre-anesthetic check-ups, detailed history, and physical examination were conducted the evening before surgery.
- Informed consent was obtained from all patients.
- ASA guidelines for preoperative fasting were followed.
- Premedication was administered with diazepam (10 mg for patients >50 kg, 5 mg for patients <50 kg) the night before and the morning of surgery.
- On the day of surgery, patients were transferred to the pre-anesthetic room and an 18 G IV cannula was secured.

2. Randomization and Group Assignment:

- Patients were randomly assigned to two groups using computer-generated numbers. Anesthesia assistants prepared the test solution according to instructions in the envelope.
- Group A: Received 5 ml of 0.75% Ropivacaine nebulization.
- Group B: Received 5 ml of 2% Lignocaine nebulization.

3. Nebulization:

- The study drugs were nebulized using a nebulizer with 100% oxygen at 10 L/min for 10 minutes in a propped-up position.
- Hemodynamic parameters (HR, SBP, DBP, MAP, SPO₂) were monitored during nebulization.

4. Intraoperative Phase:

- Patients were transferred to the operating theatre, and hemodynamic parameters were monitored every 5 minutes.
- Patients were preoxygenated for 3 minutes using 10 L/min oxygen.
- Anesthesia was induced using midazolam (0.02 mg/kg), fentanyl (2 mcg/kg), propofol (2 mg/kg), and vecuronium (0.1 mg/kg).
- Laryngoscopy was performed 3 minutes after muscle relaxant administration and intubation was done with appropriate endotracheal tube sizes.
- Hemodynamic parameters were recorded 1-, 3-, and 5-minutes post-intubation.
- Anesthesia was maintained with isoflurane (1-1.5%) and oxygen, with intermittent vecuronium doses.
- Ventilator settings were adjusted and IV paracetamol (1 gm) and fentanyl (0.5 mcg/kg every 60 minutes) were administered.

5. Extubation Phase:

- Isoflurane was stopped at the end of surgery and spontaneous ventilation mode was switched on.
- Oxygen flow was increased to 10 L/min and gentle throat suctioning was performed.

- Muscle relaxant effects were reverted with neostigmine (0.05 mg/kg) and glycopyrrolate (0.01 mg/kg).
- Patients meeting the extubation criteria were extubated and laryngeal irritation was evaluated using a 5-point rating scale.

6. Postoperative Phase:

- Hemodynamic parameters were recorded 1, 3, 5, and 10 minutes post-extubation.
- Elevated HR (>120/min) was managed with esmolol (10 mg) and elevated MAP (>120 mm Hg) with GTN (100 mcg).

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS 24. Continuous data were presented as mean (with standard deviation) or percentage; discrete data were presented as median. Hemodynamic data were analyzed using Student's independent t-test for intergroup comparison. Categorical data were analyzed using Pearson Chi-square test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 64 individuals were evaluated during the study period, divided into two groups of 32 each. The demographic characteristics of the patients, including age, gender, weight, and ASA physical status, were comparable between the two groups, ensuring that the differences observed in the outcomes were attributable to the interventions rather than baseline differences.

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic Variables

Variables	Group A	Group B	p value
Age(years)	40.19 ± 12.57	36.88 ± 9.66	0.242
Gender			
Male	10 (31.2%)	6 (18.8%)	0.248
Female	22 (68.8%)	26 (81.2%)	
Weight (kg)	62.69 ± 7.90	62.19 ± 10.01	0.825
ASA-PS			
I	24 (75%)	29 (90.6%)	0.098
II	8 (25%)	3 (9.4%)	

The baseline mean heart rate was similar between the two groups. However, significant differences emerged post-intubation and post-extubation. Group B (Lignocaine) exhibited a significantly higher mean heart rate compared to Group A (Ropivacaine) at 1 minute and 3 minutes post-extubation. This suggests that ropivacaine is more effective in attenuating the increase in heart rate associated with extubation.

Table 2: Comparison of Heart Rate (HR)

Time	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	84.66	12.31	81.84	10.00	0.32
1 minute post intubation	92.81	10.27	95.97	13.06	0.287
3 minute post intubation	84.63	13.08	90.34	14.38	0.101
5 minute post intubation	82.09	9.57	80.06	10.25	0.416
10 minute post intubation	78.53	9.00	81.97	12.22	0.205
1 minute post extubation	99.81	11.96	107.84	16.75	0.031
3 minute post extubation	89.19	19.90	100.06	13.79	0.014
5 minute post extubation	87.03	11.04	91.84	11.28	0.09
10 minute post extubation	82.28	10.04	86.38	11.03	0.126

Baseline systolic blood pressure was not significantly different between the groups. Post-intubation, Group A (Ropivacaine) showed a decrease in SBP, whereas Group B (Lignocaine) showed an increase, with the difference being

statistically significant at 1 and 3 minutes post-intubation. Similarly, post-extubation SBP was significantly lower in Group A compared to Group B at 1 and 3 minutes, indicating better control of blood pressure with ropivacaine.

Table 3: Comparison of Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP)

Time	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	129.69	9.75	124.91	12.47	0.092
1 minute post intubation	121.34	18.22	131.09	18.40	0.037
3 minute post intubation	111.94	13.70	122.88	16.29	0.005
5 minute post intubation	107.75	12.61	115.25	13.24	0.024
10 minute post intubation	111.00	12.13	116.59	18.00	0.15
1 minute post extubation	125.28	19.60	139.84	19.25	0.004
3 minute post extubation	120.59	13.86	132.00	16.08	0.003
5 minute post extubation	119.50	10.07	120.44	12.25	0.739
10 minute post extubation	115.88	11.16	117.06	23.39	0.796

There was no significant difference in baseline DBP between the groups. However, Group A had a significantly lower DBP at 1 and 3 minutes post-intubation and post-extubation compared to Group B. This suggests that ropivacaine was more effective in maintaining stable diastolic blood pressure during the peri-extubation period.

Table 4: Comparison of Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP)

Time	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	80.66	8.19	80.50	12.78	0.954
1 minute post intubation	76.03	8.94	80.97	10.43	0.046
3 minute post intubation	70.66	12.08	80.15	9.59	0.001
5 minute post intubation	68.84	11.44	72.72	13.24	0.215
10 minute post intubation	73.53	10.83	75.31	10.88	0.514
1 minute post extubation	78.72	10.23	84.56	11.40	0.035
3 minute post extubation	77.31	12.22	85.84	8.58	0.002
5 minute post extubation	76.50	9.65	79.63	10.25	0.214
10 minute post extubation	74.84	8.88	77.75	9.89	0.221

Baseline MAP was not significantly different between the groups. Post-intubation and post-extubation, Group A showed a more stable MAP compared to Group B. The difference was statistically significant at 1 and 3 minutes post-intubation and post-extubation, indicating that ropivacaine provided better control over arterial pressure changes associated with these procedures.

Table 5: Comparison of Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP)

Time	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Baseline	96.06	6.49	94.88	14.12	0.668
1 minute post intubation	90.91	10.39	98.41	12.06	0.01
3 minute post intubation	84.63	12.07	94.78	10.99	0.001
5 minute post intubation	81.84	11.94	86.59	13.87	0.147
10 minute post intubation	84.78	10.82	89.59	12.88	0.111
1 minute post extubation	94.00	12.17	102.06	13.29	0.014
3 minute post extubation	91.06	11.90	97.53	13.77	0.049
5 minute post extubation	89.56	8.31	93.50	11.76	0.127
10 minute post extubation	87.66	9.03	92.31	11.45	0.076

Laryngeal irritation was assessed in terms of coughing before and immediately after extubation. Group A showed better control over coughing with fewer incidents of grade 2 coughing compared to Group B. This indicates that ropivacaine is more effective in reducing laryngeal irritation during extubation.

Table 6: Laryngeal Irritation in Terms of Cough

Laryngeal irritation in terms of cough		Group A	Group B	p-value
Cough before extubation	Grade 1	32 (100%)	31 (96.9%)	1
	Grade 2	0	1 (3.1%)	
Cough immediately after extubation	Grade 1	31 (96.9%)	30 (93.8%)	1
	Grade 2	1 (3.1%)	2 (6.2%)	

Discussion

The study compared the effects of airway nebulization with ropivacaine versus lignocaine on intubation and extubation responses in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia. The demographic characteristics of the patients, including age, gender, weight, and ASA physical status, were similar between the two groups, ensuring that any observed differences were due to the interventions rather than baseline discrepancies.

The results demonstrated that ropivacaine nebulization was more effective than lignocaine in attenuating the increase in heart rate (HR) associated with intubation and extubation. Although the baseline HR was similar between the groups, significant differences were observed post-extubation. Group B (lignocaine) exhibited a higher mean HR compared to Group A (ropivacaine) at 1 and 3 minutes post-extubation, indicating that ropivacaine provided better control over the hemodynamic response during extubation.

Systolic blood pressure (SBP) measurements further supported these findings. Group A showed a decrease in SBP post-intubation, while Group B showed an increase, with the difference being statistically significant at 1 and 3 minutes post-intubation. Similarly, post-extubation SBP was significantly lower in Group A compared to Group B at 1 and 3 minutes. This suggests that ropivacaine was more effective in managing blood pressure changes during the peri-extubation period.

Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) followed similar trends. Group A had significantly lower DBP and MAP at 1 and 3 minutes post-intubation and post-extubation compared to Group B. These results indicate that ropivacaine was superior in maintaining stable diastolic and mean arterial pressures, contributing to overall hemodynamic stability.

In terms of laryngeal irritation, ropivacaine also proved to be more effective. Group A had fewer incidents of coughing before and immediately after extubation compared to Group B. This indicates that ropivacaine was better at reducing laryngeal irritation, making the extubation process smoother and more comfortable for patients.

Overall, the study results suggest that ropivacaine nebulization is more effective than lignocaine in managing the hemodynamic responses and

laryngeal irritation during intubation and extubation. Ropivacaine provided better control of HR, SBP, DBP, and MAP, with fewer incidences of coughing and reduced need for additional medications like esmolol and GTN. These findings highlight the potential benefits of using ropivacaine for airway nebulization in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia.

In a randomized double-blind clinical trial comparing nebulized ropivacaine (0.25%) and lignocaine (2%) for managing hemodynamic responses during intubation and extubation, it was found that ropivacaine significantly reduced mean arterial pressure (MAP) and heart rate (HR) compared to saline, with a P-value < 0.05. At extubation, the difference between ropivacaine and lignocaine in HR and MAP did not reach statistical significance (P = 0.103 and 0.153, respectively). Furthermore, 40% of patients who received ropivacaine experienced cough at extubation, compared to higher rates in the other groups (P < 0.001) [6].

Another study compared the effectiveness of intravenous lignocaine and its combination with diltiazem on hemodynamic responses during extubation. It was observed that combining lignocaine with diltiazem provided a more significant reduction in heart rate, systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and MAP at extubation and up to 10 minutes post-extubation, compared to lignocaine alone (P < 0.05) [7].

In a study investigating the effects of topical ropivacaine, it was found that this approach significantly lowered the incidence and severity of cough during extubation compared to a control group (34.62% vs. 76.92%, P = 0.002). Additionally, the sore throat visual acuity score 12 hours post-surgery was lower in the ropivacaine group (2.00 vs. 3.50, P = 0.040) [8].

Research comparing intravenous and nebulized lignocaine highlighted that while both methods were effective, intravenous lignocaine resulted in better hemodynamic stability during extubation. Nebulized lignocaine, however, remained a viable alternative, offering significant benefits in attenuating cardiovascular responses [9].

A comparative study on dexmedetomidine and lignocaine for alleviating hemodynamic responses during extubation found that dexmedetomidine (0.5

$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) was more effective than lignocaine (1.5 mg/kg) in reducing heart rate and blood pressure immediately after extubation ($P < 0.05$). Dexmedetomidine also provided deeper sedation without incidences of coughing or breath-holding [10].

Conclusion

The results indicate that ropivacaine nebulization is more effective than lignocaine in managing the hemodynamic responses and laryngeal irritation during intubation and extubation in patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia. Ropivacaine provided better control of heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressures, and mean arterial pressure, with fewer incidences of coughing and reduced need for additional medications like esmolol and GTN.

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